

**PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC
DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA:
THEORIES FOR DISTRIBUTION OF GOVERNMENT RESOURCES**

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SHORT NOTE:

Theories for Distribution of Government Resources

The pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories offer the managers of government resources two vital contemplations and scenarios in sharing government resources or public goods. The theories are postulated using two basic natural resources, such as pawpaw/papaya and pineapple fruits. Pawpaw or papaya (botanical name) and pineapple fruits are agricultural products and are considered most appropriate for use when they are fully ripped for demonstrating the sharing processes. These thoughts, as supported by Basic Resources Theory (Udoh, 2017), are advanced in attempting to resolve the surrounding issues on the concepts of equality and equity in the sharing of national and state resources in Nigeria, in particular, and the globe, in general. While the pawpaw/papaya theory has a single sharing stream, the pineapple formula has two variances, the **vertical** and the **horizontal** perspectives. The case in point is that with fiscal federalism in mind, which places a premium on how financial resources of government are shared among the federal, state and local government areas, the pawpaw/papaya theory represents equality, fairness and justice on the one hand; while pineapple theory represents equity and shrewdness on the other, respectively. In Udoh *et al*, (2018) the idea of fiscal federalism has received the endorsement of John Rawls' theory of justice whose basic assumption is on "the socially just distribution of goods in a society." A cursory and critical observation reveals that adopting the pineapple theory in financial sharing, among tiers of government is to attempt some level of subtlety and shrewdness towards the lower levels of government by the higher level of government. This is so due to the assumption that pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruit equally, at the same time, unlike pawpaw/papaya. This implies that without any careful observation of the use of the pawpaw/papaya approach in the financial sharing among tiers of government, the system or the process offers total fairness, equality and justice among all levels of government. The reason is based on the assumption that

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pawpaw rips round the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pineapples that any consumer who picks any part of the fruit

can enjoy total sweetness. The author, therefore, assures that the proper use of pawpaw theory is an antidote for a peaceful and harmonious co-existence of all the parts of a nation or state, even though it may generate bad blood among the richer components whose greater goods may serve the greater happiness of the less-rich components. However, the author warns that the use of the pineapple theory can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by the parts of a nation or state, except the horizontal variance of the pineapple theory is adopted, instead of the vertical stream. These new theories are also authenticated by the following authors: Udoh, U.S. (2014), Udoh, U.S. (2017), Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2017), Mboho, K.S. *et al* (2018) and Udoh, U.S. *et al* (2018).

KEYWORDS: *Public financial management, socio-economic development, pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories.*

THE THEORIES:

1. Pawpaw/Papaya Theory (Udoh, 2023).

- Distribution of Government Resources through Equality, Fairness and Justice

The idea behind the **Pawpaw/Papaya Theory** as a principle for the distribution of government financial resources, propounded by Dr Unwana-Abasi Udoh, a Lecturer in the Department of Public Administration at Akwa Ibom State University in 2023 represents **equality, fairness and justice**. To arrive at this conclusion, the Pawpaw/Papaya Theory is demonstrated with a fully ripped pawpaw or papaya (botanical name) fruit. The argument behind this theory is that pawpaw rips round the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pineapples. In practice, if pawpaw is peeled, sliced into smaller, but equal consumable parts and put into a bowl, it is argued that because the fruit rips round the entire body equally, at the same time, therefore, a consumer who picks any part of the fruit will enjoy the same sweetness that contains in all other parts of the fruit. Based on this premise, the author opines that, if financial operators of government adopt the Pawpaw/Papaya Theory as a guiding principle or as a sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the different parts of the nation or state, the action will result in **equality, fairness and justice**.

In this theory, therefore, the consumers do not need to know what part of the fruit was the head or tail, and what part of the bowl were the different parts of the fruit shuffled. The fact in point is that all parts of pawpaw/papaya give an equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to consumers because the fruit rips round the entire body equally, at the same time. The author, therefore, assures that the proper use of this principle is an antidote for a peaceful and harmonious co-existence of all parts of a nation or state, even though it may generate bad blood among the richer components whose greater goods may serve the greater happiness of the less-rich components.

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2. Pineapple Theory (Udoh, 2023).

- Distribution of Government Resources through **Equity** and **Shrewdness**

The **Pineapple Theory** as a principle for the distribution of financial resources, propounded by Dr Unwana-Abasi Udoh, a Lecturer in the Department of Public Administration at Akwa Ibom State University in 2023 represents **equity** and **shrewdness**.

To arrive at this conclusion, the Pineapple Theory is demonstrated with a fully ripped pineapple fruit. The term, "equity" is almost similar in meaning to "equality", except when looked at closely and properly operationalized. However, the argument behind the pineapple theory is that pineapple does not ripe round the entire body equally, at the same time, unlike pawpaw/papaya. In practice, if a pineapple is peeled, sliced into smaller, but equal consumable parts and put into a bowl, it is argued that because the pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruit equally, at the same time, a consumer must pick a part of the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness of the fruit.

Otherwise, picking a part of the tail of the fruit will soar the tongue. Based on this premise, the author argues that if financial operators adopt the Pineapple Theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the parts of the nation or state, the action will result in **equity** and **shrewdness**. Therefore, in this theory, it is only the fruitier who dressed the pineapple that knows exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail, and what part of the bowl were the different parts of the fruit shuffled. The fact in point is that not all parts of pineapple fruit give an equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to the consumers. As such, the author warns that the use of this principle can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by some parts of a nation or state, except the horizontal variance of the pineapple theory is adopted, instead of the vertical stream.

**APPLICATION OF THE PAWPAW AND PINEAPPLE THEORIES
IN RESOURCES SHARING IN NIGERIA**

1. Pawpaw/Papaya Theory:

The Pawpaw/Papaya Theory, as already said, represents **equality**, **fairness** and **justice**. The major assumption of the pawpaw/papaya theory is that if pawpaw is peeled and sliced into smaller, but equal and consumable parts, and put into a bowl, it is argued that because the fruit rips round the entire body equally, at the same time, therefore, a consumer who picks any part of the fruit will enjoy the same sweetness as contained in all other parts of the fruit. Based on this premise, the author opines that if financial operators adopt the pawpaw/papaya theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the parts of the nation or state, the action will result in equality, fairness and justice. In this theory, therefore, the consumers do not need to know exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail, and into what part of the bowl were the different parts of the fruit shuffled.

The fact in point is that all parts of pawpaw/papaya give equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to consumers. From the above assumption, the author opined that, if the

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managers of government finances or public goods adopt this method, then the different parts of the nation, states or LGs do not need any form of carefulness to know exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail, and in what part of the bowl were the different parts of the fruit shuffled before they can partake in it. This is because the sharing process with pawpaw/papaya depicts equality, fairness and justice. The reason is as earlier said, that pawpaw/papaya rips round the entire body equally, at the same time. Consumers need not be circumspect in making their choices on what parts of the fruit they have to consume.

But, adversely, the richer parts of the federation stand a chance of generating greater goods for the greater happiness of the less-richer parts. In such a situation, the government may decide to set aside the official sharing parameters such as population, land mass, ecological issues, derivation, etc. in an attempt to sympathize with those other less-richer parts of the federation in order to maintain and sustain them. That is why in some federations, monies are taken from the richer states to finance the less buoyant ones, particularly in payment of their staff salaries and retirees' pensions.

2. **Pineapple Theory:**

The pineapple theory represents **equity** and **shrewdness**. As earlier stated, the major assumption of this theory is that if a pineapple is peeled and sliced into smaller, but equal consumable parts, and into a bowl, it is argued that because the pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruit equally, at the same time, a consumer must pick a part of the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness of the fruit. Otherwise, picking a part of the tail of the fruit will leave the consumer with a soured tongue. Based on this premise, the author argues that, if financial operators adopt the pineapple theory as a guiding principle or as their sharing formula in allocating the nation's or state's financial resources to the different parts of the nation or state, the action will result in equity and shrewdness. In this theory, therefore, it is only the fruitier that will know exactly what part of the fruit is the head or tail, and what part of the bowl were the different parts of the fruit shuffled. The fact in point is that not all parts of pineapple fruit give equal and satisfying taste of sweetness to consumers. From the above assumption, there are two streams to the explanation of the pineapple approach: the **vertical** and the **horizontal** sharing formulae.

(a) In the **vertical sharing formula**, the greengrocers divide the pineapple fruit vertically into two equal parts, from head to tail before slicing them into consumable sizes. Then the sliced pieces are placed and shuffled in a bowl before consumers are allowed to partake in eating the fruit. The argument is that because the pineapple does not ripe round the entire fruit equally, at the same time, a consumer must pick a part of the head of the fruit in order to enjoy the total sweetness of the fruit. Otherwise, picking a part of tail of the fruit will leave the consumer's tongue soured. This implies that despite the official sharing parameters of government resources such as population, land mass, ecological issues,

derivation, etc. government resources can also, first of all, be shared equally. Otherwise, the equitable method of distribution of public goods is shrouded with subtlety and

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shrewdness. This situation can create room for further acrimonies and agitations on the authorities for more attention by some parts of a nation or state.

(b) But, in the **horizontal sharing formula**, the greengrocers divide the pineapple fruit horizontally into two parts, separating the head from the tail, before slicing each part into consumable sizes. The consumable pieces are equally put and shuffled in two separate bowls before consumers are allowed to partake in eating the fruit. For the sake of fairness, the slices of the tail have to be consumed separately before those of the head. But, in the horizontal sharing method, the consumers stand the chance of having a feel of the different tests of the two parts of the fruit, both soured and sweeter tastes, respectively. But, if mixed and shared, although fairness will be apparent, the resultant effect will be equity.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is interesting to note that basic natural resources that are everywhere in the environment like pawpaw/papaya and pineapple, can offer veritable instruments for scientific experimentation and solving of societal problems. The theories are postulated using basic natural resources, such as pawpaw/papaya and pineapple fruits. Pawpaw or papaya (botanical name) and pineapple fruits are agricultural products and are considered most appropriate when they are fully ripped for use in demonstrating the sharing processes. As observed in the above experiments, pawpaw/papaya and pineapple theories have become useful instruments to managers of government resources as they can use the two contemplations or scenarios in the sharing of public goods to all the components parts of the whole. For a federation like Nigeria, the managers of government resources can use the two contemplations or scenarios in the sharing of public goods to the federal, state and local government areas. To drive the point home, Udoh (2018) infers that "... every administration, be it public or private is faced with the issues of financial management in government, institutions and corporate organizations." Therefore, the author opines that "every administrator is duty-bound to manage the scarce resources at his disposal in such a manner as it is equitable and by the laid down principles."

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